

Relation Between Binding Energy and Melting Points of Lanthanide Elements

Ram Gopal* and M. M. Husain**

An attempt to calculate the binding energy, $-U_0$, of transition metal elements, was made a few years ago¹, using the metallic-valence concept of Pauling². The usual procedure of estimating the binding energy***, $-U_0$, of metals, makes use of the number of the valence-shell electrons, for 'n' in equation,

$$-U_0 = I \times n + S \quad (i)$$

in which I is the first ionisation potential and S , the latent heat of sublimation of the metal concerned; this procedure has been found to be satisfactory for simple alkali and alkaline-earth metals^{3,4} but fails completely in the transition metals⁵. The modified procedure¹, using the metallic-valence of Pauling² for 'n' in equation (i) gives reasonable values of the binding energies for these metals. It seems worthwhile to extend the application of the modified procedure to the lanthanide elements which form a group of metals closely allied in their physical properties⁶ and for most of which the required data for calculating $-U_0$, are available. The binding energy, $-U_0$, of the different lanthanide elements have been calculated from equation (i) and are given in Table I. The source of data, used in calculation, is indicated in the foot-notes of the Table.

It may be noted from Table I that the values of the binding energies of these metals lie between 400–500 kcals in most cases including lanthanum. In earlier communications¹, the general approximate proportionality of the absolute melting point T_m and the corresponding binding energy for members of a group of similar substances has been pointed out. The same should be expected for these elements as well⁶. A rough constancy of the ratio

* On leave from Lucknow University, India : Present address : Chemistry Department, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, N.C., USA.

** Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, India.

*** For the alkali and the alkaline-earth metals, this has been considered as the lattice energy (see references 4 and 5 below).

1. R. Gopal and M. M. Husain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 827; 1963, **40**, 451.
2. L. Pauling, 'Nature of the chemical bond', Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1960, p. 403.
3. O. K. Rice, 'Electronic structure and Chemical binding', McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York, 1940, p. 373.
4. J. A. A. Ketelaar, 'Chemical constitution', Elsevier Publishing Co., London, 1958, p. 322.
5. See reference 4, p. 345.
6. P. J. Durrant and B. Durrant, 'Introduction to advanced inorganic chemistry', Longmans, p. 1962, p. 1128.

$-U_0/T_m$, given in Table I, justifies this expectation although the value appears to fall-off in the higher members of the group. In view of the uncertainties of the data for I , n , and T_m and also due to transitions before the melting point, only a rough constancy should be expected. The approximate value of the ratio may be taken as 0.35. It is of interest to note that this value for alkali metals is about 0.38.

TABLE I

Element	At. No.	I(a) (e.v.)	'n' (ref., 2)	S(b)* (Kcals)	$-U_0$ (Kcals)	T_m (C) (°K)	$-U_0/T_m$
Lanthanum**	57	5.61	3	83.4	467	1193	0.40
Cerium	58	5.65	3.2	81.2	494	1070	0.46
Praseodymium	59	5.76	3	81.4	479	1208	0.40
Neodymium	60	6.31	3	71.6	507	1289	0.39
Promethium	61	—	3	—	—	1353	—
Samarium	62	5.60	3	48.6	435	1345	0.33
Europium	63	5.67	3	42.3	433	1099	0.39
Gadolinium	64	6.16	3	75.7	501	1585	0.32
Terbium	65	6.74	3.5	73.9	617	1629	0.38
Dysprosium	66	6.82	3	71.1	542	1680	0.32
Holmium	67	—	3	72.1	—	1743	—
Erbium	68	6.08(c)	3	71.1	491	1795	0.27(?)
Thulium	69	5.81(c)	3	55.4	456	1818	0.25(?)
Ytterbium	70	6.25	2	34.2	321	1089	0.31
Lutecium	71	5.00	3	79.6	425	1948	0.22(?)

(a) 'Encyclopedia of the chemical elements', Reinhold Book Corp., New York, 1968, p. 344.

(b) 'The properties of rare-earth metals and compounds', Rare-earths Research Group, Battelle Memorial Institute, 505 King Ave., Columbus, Ohio, 1959, Section I, pp. 1-2.

(c) 'Hand-book of chemistry and physics'. The Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., Cleveland, Ohio, 50th Edn., 1969-70, p. E-74.

* Sum of the latent heats of fusion and evaporation. No attempt has been made to include the heat changes involved in heating from 0°K to T_m as this would not affect $-U_0$ values to any significant extent.

** It is included in this study as its properties are similar to lanthanides although La is not included in this group.

† The values of I and T_m , for these metals, from different sources, differ in many cases. For example, I for neodymium is given as 6.31(a) and 5.51(c); for terbium as 6.74(a) and 5.98(c). The T_m also differs somewhat in some cases. The boiling points (although not used here but they give an idea of the uncertainties involved) differ considerably, e.g., for lanthanum, the values given are 3454° (a) and 4515° (c), for thulium as 1727° (a) and 2400° (b) and for ytterbium as 1193° (a) and 1427° (b and c). (a), (b) and (c) refer to references in Table I and temperatures are in °C. Other sources give still different values cf. F. H. Spedding and A. H. Danne, 'The Rare-earths', John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1961, p. 184. Also the Pauling's metallic valency, on which $-U_0$ depend to a large extent, is only a rough estimate. Under these conditions, a rough constancy of $-U_0/T_m$ given in Table, should be considered good enough for the present purposes. No exact quantitative significance should be attached to $-U_0$ values.

The results obtained here may be used to make some reasonable guess about the values of ionisation potentials of members for which they are not known or not known with certainty. For example, I for holmium should be about 6–7 e.v., for lutecium about 6–7 e.v. and for promethium about 6 e.v. The value of I , for lutecium given in Table I as 5.0, appears to be too low, considering the high T_m and S of this element. Also the values of I for erbium and thulium, quoted in Table I, appear to be lower by about one e.v. It is assumed that the Pauling's valency is as given in Table I.

The actinide series of elements should also behave in the same manner and it would be interesting to use the present procedure to estimate the binding energy and its relation to T_m for these elements. Such an attempt will have to wait until the required data are available.

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Chemistry Departments,
UNC, Chapel Hill, N.C., USA,
and
Lucknow University,
Lucknow, U.P., India.

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